

OPTIMIZATION OF PROCESS PARAMETERS ANALYSIS OF FRICTION DRILLING ON MS AND AL 1008 BY USING ROTATING CONICAL TOOL

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Abstract

In the thermal drilling process friction heat generated between conical tool and workpiece is used to make a hole in sheet metal operation, square metallic tube, circular tube, hard materials, and composite materials. This is a bur free operation with a natural formation bush that will be useful in form threading process and sheet metal operation.

Keywords: Material, Temperature, Bush length, surface roughness and Hardness

1. Introduction

In the thermal drilling process centre region of the tool comes in contact with the workpiece due to thrust force friction generated between the workpiece and centre region of the tool. Friction between the center region of the tool and workpiece heat the workpiece, the workpiece is in a plastic state at the same time the centre region of the tool penetrates the workpiece. Due to that penetration plastic deformation of material take place and naturally formed collar and bush in the workpiece without the formation of the chip. The material removal takes place by melting and vaporization without the use of coolant so it is a bur-free operation. Thermal drilling has a wide range of applications in the manufacturing, thermal, design, aerodynamic, and biomedical area.

Working Principal

In the friction, drilling process centre region of the tool comes in contact with the workpiece due to thrust force friction generated between the workpiece and centre region of the tool. Friction between the centre region of the tool and workpiece heat the workpiece, the workpiece is in a plastic state at the same time the centre region of the tool penetrates the workpiece. The conical tool has cylindrical, collar, and shank regions. The conical region of the tool produces a naturally formed bush in the workpiece while the collar of the tool produces a naturally formed boss over the friction-drilled hole. Naturally, formed bush and boss have a wide range of applications in sheet metal operation. The formation of bush completely depends on the thickness of material if the thickness of material is 't' bush formed in materials is 3 times t. The formation of bush and boss also depends on the type of materials. During the friction, drilling process if we preheat the workpiece will get the proper formation of bush and boss formation in a workpiece.

Friction Tool geometry

Friction drilling tool having 5 regions each region of friction drilling tool contributing during the friction drilling process.

1) Centre region 2) Conical region 3) Cylindrical region 4) Shoulder region 5) Shank region

Centre region –Centre region has angle α and height h_c and the angle are blunt that blunting produce more force due to more force heat generated between the tool and the workpiece.

Conical region- Conical region helps to penetrate the workpiece.

Cylindrical region- Cylindrical region of the tool guides the bush throughout the length of the bush.

Shoulder region – Creates boss over the friction drilled hole

Shank region-Shank region used to hold the tool in the tool holder

Fig1: Friction Tool geometry

Literature survey

1. Han-Ming Chow et.al: Optimized the friction drilling parameters by using the Taguchi method. Optimized parameters further they have used in the calculation, at the end they have concluded that friction drilling is a chipless process, on the polluted process, short machining cycle required, whole quality get is better than that of the twist drilling process and friction drilling tool having high tool life than that of twist drill.

2. Shayan Dehgan et.al: Done the friction drilling on hard materials followed by friction drilling they have done the CAE analysis of friction drilling hole to analyze the friction drilling hole, to analyze the bush, and to check the surface finish produced after friction drilling.

3. N.Srilatha et.al : The author analyzes the different parameters during friction drillings like bush quality, surface temperature, speed, feed, torque, tool wear, thrust force, and effect of tool

and workpiece contact area.

4.P.V.Shalomov et.al : In this paper, the author identified that in friction drilling process has five stages also it identified that material hardening takes place at the heating zone, seen that shear strength is higher than the estimated, the height and thickness of upper and lower flanging reduces.

5. Ahuja .B.B et.al: Author optimized the friction drilling parameters like tool diameter, feed, and speed also measures the responses such as surface roughness, dimensional error, statistical analysis and develop empirical model for responses.

6. N. Rajesh Jesudoss Hyness et.al: In this paper, the author analyzed the thermal behaviour of materials and studied the numerical analysis of the process also calculated the heat flux and temperature distribution between tool and workpiece.

Selection of input Parameters

Input parameter selected based on Taguchi design table and based on responses to do the form drilling on workpiece material selecting the input parameter based on responses such as Speed, Feed, Material, parting paste, and tool diameters.

1. Responses

Responses selected based on inputs are Bush length, Hardness, Temperature

1.1. Material Selection

The material selection depends on the high applications of materials in the industry like hard materials, composite materials, and PVC materials. The material is in square tube form having the same thickness. The thickness will depend on the formability and easy availability of the material in the local market. The material used for experiment purposes is chosen in such a way that they have high application in automobile and industrial areas. The c/s also so chosen that is square pipes 40×40 mounting is easy to hold to the jaws of the fixture. Materials required good properties which are helpful while doing friction drilling process. For experimentation purpose selected Mild steel and AISI 1008 Aluminium as a material and carried out friction drilling on it.

Selection of Tools

The selection of tools depends up on the type of input and output parameters and also the type of material used in the friction drilling process.

Stages of friction drilling process

Heat affected Zone

Stage-I

Stage-II

Stage-III

2. Process Parameter table

Level	Speed (rpm)	Feed (mm/min)	Material (Type)
1	2000	50	AISI 1008 Al
2	3500	80	MS
3	5000	110	-

2.1 Experimental design table

Expt. no.	Material (Type)	Speed (rpm)	Feed (mm/min)	TEMP (°c)	BL (mm)	HV (hv)	Temp SNR (db)	BL SNR (db)	HV SNR (db)
1	1	1	1	378	11.46	58.67	51.5498	21.19	-35.37
2	1	1	2	468	10.2	55.33	53.4049	20.17	-34.86
3	1	1	3	427	10.3	61.33	52.6085	20.25	-35.75
4	1	2	1	377	10.29	68	51.526	20.24	-36.65
5	1	2	2	555	10.27	61.67	54.8858	20.23	-35.80
6	1	2	3	437	10.15	68.67	52.8096	20.13	-36.73
7	1	3	1	540	10.27	67.33	54.6478	20.23	-36.56
8	1	3	2	506	10.39	57	54.0830	20.33	-35.11
9	1	3	3	507	10.39	62.67	51.0289	20.33	-35.94
10	2	1	1	396	11.37	139.33	51.9539	21.11	-42.88
11	2	1	2	353	10.29	162.33	50.9554	20.25	-44.21
12	2	1	3	280	10.11	161.33	48.9431	20.09	-44.15
13	2	2	1	373	10.18	147.33	51.4341	20.15	-43.36
14	2	2	2	227	10.26	126.67	47.1205	20.22	-42.05
15	2	2	3	219	10.18	147.33	46.8088	20.15	-43.36
16	2	3	1	394	11.26	150.67	51.9099	21.03	-43.56
17	2	3	2	278	11.38	175.33	48.8808	21.12	-44.87
18	2	3	3	257	11.38	151.67	48.1986	21.12	-43.61

2.2 S/N Ratio graphs For Temperature

SN RATIOS GRAPH TEMPERATURE(°C)

S/N graph for Tem

Level	Material (Type)	Speed (rpm)	Feed (mm/min)
1	53.29	51.57	52.17
2	49.58	50.76	51.56
3		51.97	50.58
Delta	3.71	1.27	1.59
Rank	1	3	2

**Optimum Parameter
Setting :M1S3F1**

SN RATIOS AND MEANS GRAPH FOR BUSH LENGTH

SN GRAPH FOR BUSH LENGTH (mm)

Optimum Parameter Setting :M2S3F1

SN RATIOS AND MEANS GRAPH FOR HARDNESS

SN GRAPH MEANS FOR HARDNESS(Hv)

OPTIMUM PARAMETER SETTING :M1S2F1

2.3 Optimization of process parameters

Optimization of input parameter by using linear programming (by using LPP software)

$$\text{Temp} = f(S, F)$$

$$2000 \geq S \leq 5000$$

$$50 \geq F \leq 110$$

The objective function selected for Maximization is

$$\text{LogTp} = 2.6645 + 0.2633S + 0.08972F$$

$$Z = \text{LogTp} = 2.6645 + 0.2633S + 0.08972F$$

$$|Z|_{\text{Maximise}} = 2.6645 + 0.2633S + 0.08972F$$

The objective function selected for Minimization is

$$\text{Hardness} = f(S, F)$$

$$\text{LogHv} = 1.79328 + 0.0821S - 0.00774F$$

$$Z = \text{LogHv} = 1.79328 + 0.0821S - 0.00774F$$

$$|Z|_{\text{Minimise}} = 1.79328 + 0.0821S - 0.00774F$$

The objective function selected for Maximization is

$$\text{LogBl} = 1.01732 - 0.035S - 0.047F$$

$$Z = \text{LogBl} = 1.01732 - 0.035S - 0.047F$$

$|Z|_{\text{Maximise}} = 1.01732 - 0.035S - 0.047F$

For Temp Maximization

Hardness Minimization

Table no 2.3 optimization of input parameters

Responses	Optimum values of parameters for material A and B.	
	Speed(rpm)	Feed(mm/min)
Temp1	5000	110
Hardness 1	2000	110
Bush Length1	5000	50
Temp2	5000	50
Hardness2	2000	50
Bush Length2	5000	50

From S/N graphs for Material (mm), Temperature (°c), and Hardness (hv)

The summarized optimum conditions are as below:

Table 2.4: Summary of optimised conditions

Responses	Material	Spindle speed	Feed	Optimum Parameters setting
	Type	rpm	mm/min	
Temperature(°c)	1	3	1	M1S3F1
Bush Length(mm)	2	3	1	M2S3F1
Hardness(hv)	1	2	1	M1S2F1

2.5 conclusions during comparative study

- The optimum parameter settings found according to the Taguchi analysis are M1S3F1, M2S3F1, and M1S2F1 for Temperature(°C), Bush Length(mm) and Hardness(Hv) respectively.
- The maximum Temp got for material A is 480 °C and for material B is 320 °C, maximum Bush length for material A is 10.42 mm and for Material B is 11.02 mm and Minimum Hardness for material A is 55 Hv and for material B is 139.33 Hv.
- The major factors with their % contribution affecting the Temperature, Bush Length and Hardness are Speed(95%), Material type (57%) and Feed (26%).
- The separate equation each for temperature, hardness and bush length depending upon the material type have been derived in order to judge their performance in friction drilling operation.

Table 2.5: Comparative study Regression equations in coded Form

Temperature (°c)	$T_p = 10^{0.03981} \times M_t^{2.6037} \times S^{-0.0927} \times F^{0.01008}$
Hardness (hv)	$H_v = 10^{0.0049} \times M_t^{1.9875} \times S^{0.19304} \times F^{0.01023}$
Bush Length (mm)	$Bl = 10^{0.0078} \times M_t^{0.9965} \times S^{0.006} \times F^{0.0046}$

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